

Springcreek Project, Miami County (40.06820, -84.21191)

Since construction in 2021, the main nutrient benefit of the Springcreek Project has been filtering inflows from Spring Creek and the Great Miami River. However, the nutrient filtration capacity of this Project has been limited by the dry weather conditions of 2023 and 2024 decreasing annual stream flows. Each year there were only two offloading events to the wetlands, which resulted in filtration of 4.8 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2023 and 1.6 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2024. The Project also contributes 0.8 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source. In 2024, the total retention was 2.5 lbs phosphorus per acre (1.6 + 0.8)

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (25 acres of restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland consisting of two wetland pools that are connected to one-another by a channel. The North Pool exchanges water with Spring Creek, while the South Pool exchanges water with the Great Miami River. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which the Great Miami River and Spring Creek flood the wetland pools, possible at discharges of at least 5,229 cubic feet per second (cfs) and 203 cfs, respectively.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Lower the Great Miami River inflow notch would allow for more connectivity but less storage capacity during very high flow events, such that a balance would need to be found between capturing high and low flow events while also retaining water long enough for nutrient reductions to occur.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.